

MODIFIED IODOMETRIC METHOD FOR THE ESTIMATION OF ZINC

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Zinc can be estimated iodometrically with the help of potassium ferricyanide and potassium iodide in acetate-acetic acid buffer medium if p_H of the solution is maintained between 3 and 4. The excess ferricyanide concentration in solution should not exceed 2-mM/litre.

The iodometric method for the estimation of zinc was first used by Lang (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 79, 161) in a slightly acidic solution, adding small amounts of ferricyanide at a time. The results were about 1.65% lower than the stoichiometric value. Mann and Swift (*Anal. Chem.*, 1949, 21, 798) added the ferricyanide in one lot and adjusted the p_H of the medium between 2 and 3 with phthalate buffer. They could estimate a minimum of 65 mg. of zinc accurately. Their stoichiometrically calculated values had to be multiplied by 1.019 to provide correct values. A large excess of ferricyanide, however, afforded higher results, particularly with smaller amounts of zinc. In the present work, the effects of p_H and the excess ferricyanide concentration have been studied with acetate-acetic acid buffer medium.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagent grade chemicals were always used. The stock solution of approximately 0.1M sodium thiosulphate was standardised against potassium iodate from time to time. Approximately 0.1M solution of potassium ferricyanide was prepared in cold distilled water and was kept in dark when not in use. Anhydrous zinc sulphate was prepared by heating 'Analar' quality hydrated zinc sulphate to $300^\circ \pm 5^\circ$. Solutions of zinc sulphate were made by weight from this sample. The strength was also checked by precipitating and weighing as zinc ammonium phosphate.

In order to study the effect of the excess of ferricyanide on iodide in the acetate-acetic acid medium, several experiments (without zinc) were performed at p_H 3, 4 and 5 approximately, taking different amounts of ferricyanide, while keeping the iodide concentration and the total volume of the solution the same. Iodine liberated after 10 minutes in dark was estimated. When the p_H of the solution was approximately between 3 and 4 and the ferricyanide added did not exceed 2 mM per litre, no iodine was found to be liberated within 10 minutes.

The actual method employed for the estimation of zinc is shown below. The results obtained with different amounts of zinc, both at p_H 3 and 4, are shown in Table I, from which the amount of zinc found appears to be always less than the amount taken. The plot of the amount of zinc, found by calculation, against the amount taken, gave a straight line in each set of experiments. From the plots the average multiplication factor came out to be 1.020. A minimum of 30 mg. of zinc could be estimated by this method. It may be mentioned that the addition of ammonium sulphate rapidly coagulates the precipitate, rendering a sharper end-point. If p_H exceeds 4, the end-point becomes unstable.

TABLE I

Expt. No.	p_H of the solu.	Ferricyanide added.	Ferricyanide in excess.	Thiosulphate required (m e.).	*Zn found.	**Zinc found.	Zn taken.
I (a)	(4 $\pm$ 0.2) approx.	4.3 c.c.	1.0 c.c.	0.3016	0.02956 g.	0.03015 g.	0.03016 g.
(b)	"	7.6	"	0.6034	0.0591	0.06029	0.06032
(c)	"	17.5	"	1.508	0.1478	0.1508	0.1508
II (a)	(4 $\pm$ 0.2) approx.	8.3	5.0	0.3027	0.0296	0.03026	0.03016
(b)	"	11.5	"	0.6043	0.0592	0.06040	0.06032
(c)	"	18.0	"	1.205	0.1181	0.1205	0.1206
(d)	"	21.5	"	1.508	0.1478	0.1508	0.1508
III (a)	(3 $\pm$ 0.2) approx.	4.3	1.0	0.3016	0.0205	0.03015	0.03016
(b)	"	7.6	"	0.6034	0.0591	0.06029	0.06032
(c)	"	17.5	"	1.508	0.1478	0.1508	0.1508
IV (a)	(3 $\pm$ 0.2) approx.	8.5	5.0	0.3260	0.0319	0.03296	0.03246
(b)	"	12.5	"	0.6463	0.0638	0.06510	0.06492
(c)	"	23.0	"	1.620	0.1589	0.1621	0.1623

* Stoichiometrically.

** Using the multiplying factor.

Measured volumes of zinc sulphate solution containing different amounts of zinc along with KI (3 g.), ammonium sulphate (5-10 g.) and 50 c.c. of approximately molar ammonium acetate were taken in 500 c.c. stoppered bottles. About 45 c.c. of $N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ (to adjust the p_H between 3 and 4) and necessary amount of water to make the volume up to about 250 c.c. were added. A calculated amount of potassium ferricyanide ($\sim 0.1M$) solution (depending upon the amount of zinc present in solution; cf. Table I) was added in one lot, such that the excess ferricyanide concentration in solution did not exceed 2 millimoles per litre. (When the zinc content of the solution is unknown, a rough experiment may be performed with sufficiently large excess of ferricyanide). The mixture was swirled and kept in dark for 5 minutes. It was then taken out and titrated against a standard thiosulphate solution to the conventional starch iodide end-point. The amount of zinc calculated stoichiometrically multiplied by the factor 1.020 gives the actual amount of zinc in solution.